

Impact of Artificial Intelligence in Education

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Abstract

The main purpose of this article was to reveal the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) in education. Though the development of AI is still in the early stage, it magnificently plays a significant role in this sector. Several articles have been reviewed to fulfill the purpose. According to the findings, the impact was separated into two individual categories which were (1) positive impact, and (2) negative impact. Later, they were divided into some sub-categories to evaluate the findings more explicitly. In short, this article has reviewed several impacts including personalized learning, intelligent tutoring systems, distance education, automated grading, and feedback, chatbots, virtual reality, and many more. Similarly, financial issues, unemployment problems, and unethical issues have been presented as negative impacts here. With constantly mentioning the positive and negative impacts, the article delivers a complete overview of the impacts of AI in the education sector.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Education, Impact, Personalized Learning, Adaptive Learning

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Chapter 1 : INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Artificial intelligence has been a common phrase in modern days (Krstić et al., 2022). Unlike other sectors, it has been playing a significant role in the education sector too. However, artificial intelligence can be mentioned as the replication of human that has the ability to think and act like a human (Al Braiki et al., 2020; Wartman & Combs, 2018). Similarly, artificial intelligence in education (AIED) is a computer which can perform similarly to human minds, especially for learning and problem-solving (Baker and Smith, 2019).

When we mention a traditional school system, there are several things to mention. Like, in a traditional school system, there is a person whose job responsibility is to do the teaching. We call them a teacher. Similarly, there are also some other people available who are keen to learn and enrich their knowledge. They are known as a student. So, it is the teacher's main responsibility to teach the students. But a teacher needs to do some other tasks besides teaching. For example, creating and updating the curriculum, course planning, and evaluating the students (Ahmad et al., 2022). These tasks are often time-consuming. As a result, the teacher is not able to do the main mandatory task he must need to do. Moreover, in a traditional school system, the one-size-fits-all approach is being followed. According to the procedure, a syllabus or a course plan needs to be followed by all individual students. As a result, a student does not get the right knowledge. Therefore, the functioning of a school system is not being met properly. But those problems can be solved with the help of artificial intelligence in education.

1.2 Motivation of the Study

Artificial intelligence has become a trending topic in recent days. Many researches from different countries showing the inference between artificial intelligence and education

and it's positive and negative effects which is a key feature to discuss in this article. This will be done by reviewing the literature done by different authors on artificial intelligence in education and pointing out the effects of artificial intelligence on education.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

Since artificial intelligence is evolving day by day, and since it is having a great influence on every sector lately, it can undoubtedly be ensured that it can also have a great impact on the education sector. AI can provide impact on every possible situation in education, especially academic tasks. The purpose of this article is to explore the impact of AI on the field of education. More specifically, the article will explore both positive and negative impacts simultaneously in order to get a clear overview. This will be done by reviewing the literature done by different authors on artificial intelligence in education and pointing out the effects of artificial intelligence on education.

Chapter 2 : LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Impact of Artificial Intelligence in Education

Artificial intelligence has been proving its worth in the field of education for quite some time. It is actively keeping an impact in both academic and administrative sectors of school management (Ahmad et al., 2022). Similarly, according to (Celik et al., 2022) study, it is vivid that artificial intelligence can provide impact in enhancing teacher's capabilities with helping in planning, implementation, and assessment. For example, artificial intelligence can profile a student, and based on that, it can predict an adaptive educational environment for that particular student (Mijwil et al., 2022). Moreover, it enables automated grading in student assessment and providing feedback (Kaya & Bulut, 2022). As a result, the teacher is getting much time to teach his students, explaining all the topics elaborately, and giving instant feedbacks to the students. The students are also getting properly tailored feedback based on their performance which enhance the students' knowledge, capabilities, and effectiveness.

The authors (Xia et al., 2022) pointed out some artificial intelligence roles and their outcomes in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: The Roles of AI in Education

In short, artificial intelligence in education is benefiting us in a variety of ways (Ahmad et al., 2020; Devi et al., 2022; Hashim et al., 2022; Kaya et al., 2022; Krstić et al., 2022; Mijwil et al., 2022; Nalbant, 2021; Remian, 2019; Akinwalere & Ivanov, 2022). Such as (1) Personalized and Adaptive Learning, (2) Adaptive Learning with Special Needs, (3) Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS), (4) Distance Education, (5) Automated Grading and Feedback, (6) Chatbots, (7) Virtual Reality (VR) & Augmented Reality (AR), (8) Intelligent Teaching Robots, (9) Retention and Dropout Prediction.

2.1.1 Positive Impacts of Artificial Intelligence in Education

2.1.1.1 Personalized and Adaptive Learning

Personalized Learning is an educational approach that ensures a tailored instruction, content, environment based on each and every student's individual needs. In a classroom, there are several students with different attitudes. Each of them has their own needs. A teacher can't fulfill all of those needs and that's where artificial

intelligence kicks in (Nigar, N.,2022; Nalbant, 2021). Artificial intelligence can predict a student's need at first and based on the result, it can suggest and provide the appropriate content (Huang et al., 2023; Krstić et al., 2022; Zhai et al., 2021). As a result, individual needs and goals can be achieved using personalized learning models (Shemshack et al. ,2020). Algorithms like artificial neural networks (ANNs) are used in adaptive learning to imitate human cognitive functionality to predict students' needs at the very beginning (Southgate et al., 2019). It can also take data from students, analyze them and find out students' needs (Martin Nunez & Diaz Lantada, 2020). Similarly, it follows a personalized education model to complete the task (Kaya & Bulut, 2022). Moreover, student's profiling model can be used to generate a tailored personalized and adaptive learning (Missaoui and Maalel, 2021). According to their study, it can be achieved by following three phases which is illustrated in Figure 2.2. The following three phases are 1. Data collection, 2. Data representation, and 3. Student profiling. In the first phase which is data collection, data is collected from various sources, including questionnaires, databases, observations, existing records and weblog. Then in next phase, the collected data are represented in the system by building a semantic student profiling. It is a representation of the student's knowledge, capabilities and skills. After that in final phase, it uses machine learning techniques to analyze students' characteristics and providing prediction based on the analysis.

Figure 2.2: Student Profile Modeling Model

Recommender systems can be used to accomplish personalized and adaptive learning (Ahmad et al., 2020). In addition, students can adapt to the tools easily as they have access to the tools completely (Hashim et al., 2022). Moreover, an adaptive learning environment can be created with artificial intelligence so that students will have a similar experience to real-world environment (Mijwil et al., 2022). It is proven that students are getting better grades in artificial education-based education (Akgun et al., 2021). In short, personalized and adaptive learning can enhance student models significantly (Nassoura, 2022). In addition, personalized learning can enable customized instruction, improve the engagement of students to study, and enhance flexibility (Pendy, 2021). However, according to (Bulger, 2016), 5 types of personalized learning systems are available to use.

5 Types of Personalized Learning Systems

Figure 2.3: 5 Types of Personalized Learning Systems

Personalized learning can be achieved and implemented using these approaches which is mentioned in Figure 2.3. Figure 2.4 illustrated different types of tools which are being used to ensure personalized learning in the education sector (Chassignol et al., 2018; Ahmad et al., 2020; Krasheninnik et al., 2022).

Figure 2.4: Personalized Learning Tools

2.1.1.2 Personalized Learning with Special Needs

It is artificial intelligence that can be used as a tremendous opportunity for students with special needs. (Garg and Sharma, 2020) pointed out some signs to explain problems associated with child which are learning problem, not accepted by other children, children with disabilities, faces rejection from a teacher, and cannot adjust in school. Similarly, according to (Ojha,2022), students who have dyslexia, ADHD, sensory/physical impairment, autism, and cerebral palsy can be categorized as student who needs special need. With the help of artificial intelligence, students who are suffering from autism, or dyslexia can be taught at the same school as a regular student (Devi et al., 2022). Narrator, voice-to-text features can be used for students with special needs for better reading and writing (Nigar, N.,2022; Remian, 2019). In addition, electronic magnifiers, Braille note-takers, and Braille typewriters can be utilized with visual impairment which will help students with special needs to study (Kaya et al., 2022).

2.1.1.3 Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS)

Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) can be a great alternative to human tutoring. These ITS systems are designed based on a knowledge-based domain (Ahmad et al., 2020). ITS is a computer-based system that can assure personalized assistance to students (Pendy, 2021). A student can take full support from the system and the system will provide instant feedback to the student which cannot be possible with human tutoring (Southgate et al., 2019). According to (Remian, 2019), ITS can accomplish two things e.g. monitoring a student's progress and based on that it can adjusting the contents. Figure 2.5 illustrated some tools and platforms which can be to ensure intelligent tutoring system (Ahmad et al., 2020; Chen et al.,2020).

Figure 2.5: Intelligent Tutoring System's Tools/Platforms

2.1.1.4 Distance Education

In a traditional school system, a student has to learn from his teacher at a given time at a certain place. As the given time is short, it is not possible to fulfill the student's demands completely. An artificial intelligence tool can help to get rid of this particular problem. Artificial intelligence has enabled online learning as a result a student can be taught from anywhere at any time (Krstić et al., 2022; Kaya & Bulut, 2022). Moreover, it has introduced to us an E-learning platform as a result the particular room-based classroom has turned into a global classroom. A student can get self-learning with the help of E-learning after the counseling hour with his teacher. Figure 2.6 illustrated E-learning platforms which are being used to perform E-learning in education sector (Dimitriadou et al., 2023).

Figure 2.6: E-Learning Platforms

Moreover, (Al Braiki et al., 2020; Hashim et al., 2022) mentioned “Massive open online course (MOOC)” which may play a vital role in the E-learning sector. Using those platforms, people from different languages can join a single class together and can able to learn different languages’ offered knowledge (Nalbant, 2021; Akinwalere & Ivanov, 2022).

2.1.1.5 Automated Grading and Feedback

In a traditional school system, it is a common scenario to take some tests after teaching a lesson to measure what he has learned so far. To do so, a single teacher has to evaluate more than 20-30 students’ papers in a short time. So, a teacher can’t emphasize all the students’ papers properly and equally as time is ticking. Moreover, after grading the papers, the teacher needs to provide feedback based on each student’s performance. Based on the provided feedback, a student can acknowledge that his performance was whether enough or not. He can also learn where he needs to improve if his performance doesn’t meet the demands (Kaya et al., 2022). But it is quite difficult for a teacher to provide 20-30 students separately.

Artificial intelligence can be a savior to resolve this issue. It gives instant feedback based on the student's performance using an artificial neural network (Zhai et al., 2021). The teachers will also be notified about students' progress and feedback about how to do better (Fahimirad and Kotamjani, 2018). Artificial intelligence can assist to compute self-assessment by taking multiple-choice and fill-in-the-gaps which makes it possible to automate grading (Martin Nunez & Diaz Lantada, 2020). Similarly, (Al Braiki et al., 2020) explained that automated grading can be managed in two possible ways such as multiple-choice questions and automated essay scoring. In addition, (González-Calatayud et al., 2021) found that automated grading can be taken in some different manners. For example, virtual reality and augment reality can be used to detect and analyze students' movements in dental education where a student can be graded based on their efficiency. Similarly, answering questions can also be an alternative way for automated grading. Furthermore, "Artificial Intelligence Teaching System (AUTS)" can be used which automatically can grade a student's assessment (Martin Nunez & Diaz Lantada, 2020). According to the research conducted by (Chen et al., 2020), AIWBEs programs deliver grading guides so that it is much easier to grade students. In addition, the author found that Knewton program can offer splendid feedback to the student. The study by (Nigar, N., 2022) revealed that an animation system can be used to provide feedback based on students' work. Following this approach, a primary student has shown animation and he has to elaborate on it in his own words while maintaining consistency. Later based on that student's answer script, a new animation will be created to evaluate the script using animation. (Nassoura, 2022) found a tool, named M-Write, which can evaluate a student's work, capable to find out the wrong spots in writing and also weak points in writing. Figure 2.7 illustrated tools/platforms which can automate grading and provide feedbacks (Ahmad et al., 2020).

Figure 2.7: Students' Grading & Evaluation Tools/Platforms

Moreover, (Akgun et al.,2021) revealed that a tool named Gradescope, is being used to evaluate students' work in various universities. The author also found that open online courses like Coursera and EdX has automated scoring engines to evaluate one's work. Similarly, (Remian, 2019) also mentioned using Gradescope tool for automated grading. According to (Baidoo-Anu et al., 2023), a chatbot, named ChatGPT, can be used for automated grading too.

2.1.1.6 Chatbots

Chatbots have become one of the most trending topics in recent years. A chatbot, which is also a conversational agent, is being used to simulate conversations which allows one to have a conversation using a message service (Dimitriadou et al., 2023). In a school system, it may act as a teaching assistant, learning partner or as personal tutor (Deng et al.,2023). Chatbots can be used for many purposes in the education sector. For example, a chatbot that is created based on language models, named ChatGPT, can be utilized to achieve personalized tutoring, Language Translation, Interactive Learning, Adaptive

Learning, etc. (Baidoo-Anu et al., 2023). Similarly, according to (Sok and Heng, 2023), the ChatGPT chatbot is able to perform 5 individual tasks. For example, creating learning assessments, enriching pedagogical practice, offering virtual personal tutoring, creating an outline, and also brainstorming ideas. Moreover, the chatbot can offer a personalized service for both teachers and students (Okonkwo and Ade-Ibijola, 2021). In addition, these chatbots can help a student as they can detect anxiety and depression (Salas-Pilco and Yang, 2022). Some famous chatbots are illustrated in Figure 2.8 (Dimitriadou et al., 2023).

Figure 2.8: Chatbot Platforms

(Ahmad et al.,2022) outlined a detailed structure of Chatbot and how it functions which is illustrated in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9: Detailed Structure of Chatbot

2.1.1.7 Virtual Reality (VR) & Augmented Reality (AR)

Virtual reality allows one to create simulations similar to the real world (Ahmad et al., 2022). It can be used in the education sector to make education quite simpler. A course or subject can be risky to learn in real life or the necessary equipment can be costly as well (Ahmad et al., 2022). Virtual reality can be used in those scenarios by simulating a virtual environment like the real world with realistic sounds and images (Mijwil et al., 2022). It has a high demand in the military, defense, medical, and pilot fields (Nalbant, 2021). Moreover, it is being used in mathematics, physics, biochemistry, and marine education as well (Dimitriadou et al., 2023). The author (Asad et al., 2021) found that virtual reality can act as a pedagogical tool to enrich students' experimental learning. The author also mentioned that it can be used for reading and writing skills, and communication as well. In addition, (Guan et al., 2020) revealed that virtual reality can enhance student engagement who are self-directed and digital expert students. Similarly, augmented reality can be helpful to enhance students' learning (Lee, 2012;

Garzón, Pavón, & Baldiris, 2019; Kesim and Ozarslan, 2012). With the help of augmented reality (AR), computer-generated virtual imagery data can be superimposed on a live, immediate, or indirect real-world environment (Lee, 2012). It can visualize extra information in real world environment using 3D which can help a student to gain more knowledge on a specific topic (Nalbant, 2021). Collaborative tasks can also be enhanced using augment reality (Kesim and Ozarslan, 2012).

2.1.1.8 Intelligent Teaching Robots

As artificial intelligence can ensure personalized learning and can evaluate a student's performance, it can be considered an alternative version of a human teacher (Fahimirad et al., 2018). Moreover, a teacher can take using intelligent roots for managing teaching (Mijwil et al., 2022). Sometimes it is better to have an intelligent teaching robot, rather than a human teacher. For instance, the intelligent robots will not have any feelings similar to anger, or impatience. As a result, a student can ask the same questions over again and again. The intelligent robot will patiently answer all of the questions elaborately (Kaya et al., 2022). Moreover, it will be available 24/7 when a human teacher can be absent due to illness or personal problems (Kaya et al., 2022). The author (Krstić et al., 2022) mentioned that educational robots can be used to improve students' analytical, creative, and practical skills. Figure 2.9 illustrated some example of intelligent teaching robots (Chassignol et al., 2018).

Figure 2.10: Intelligent Teaching Robots

2.1.1.9 Retention and Dropout Prediction

Retention and Dropout rates can be predicted with the help of artificial intelligence in education. Moreover, the Random Forest algorithm has been used to find out the retention rates of an institution (Ahmed et al., 2020). Similarly, artificial intelligence can be used to search for those who are suffering and struggling during taking lessons so that they can get help before considering dropout (Nassoura, 2022). Figure 2.11 illustrated some platforms/tools which are able to predict students' retention, dropout, and performance (Ahmad et al., 2020).

Figure 2.11: Retention, Dropout & Performance Prediction Tools/Platforms

2.1.1.10 Other Impacts of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence can play a vital role in many ways in the education sector. For example, (Pendy, 2021) noted that gamification might be an option to ensure a tailored education system. Similarly, (Krstić et al., 2022) mentioned that artificial intelligence can be used for teaching evaluation. It can detect a classroom's management of whether students are paying attention to their lesson or not. Moreover, (Mijwil et al., 2022) denoted that artificial intelligence can be used to define the classroom weakness so that the available teacher can take necessary steps. Additionally, multiple studies (Mijwil et al., 2022; Ahmad et al., 2022; Salas-Pilco & Yang, 2022; Nassoura, 2022; Chen et al., 2020) collectively highlight the significance of smart content creation in the education sector. It represents virtual content similar to digital books, video lectures, etc. (Ahmad et al., 2020) also reported that artificial intelligence can provide a vital impact in classroom monitoring. The author also mentioned some AI-based tools or platforms related to classroom monitoring and visual analysis which are illustrated in Figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12: Classroom Monitoring & Visual Analysis related Tools/Platforms

According to (Huang et al., 2023), artificial intelligence can be used to learn in language learning. It can help one to learn in writing, reading, vocabulary and grammar, speaking and listening.

2.1.2 Negative Impacts of Artificial Intelligence in Education

2.1.2.1 Lack of Emotion

It is already found that artificial intelligence has no kind of emotions. As a result, shy and introverted students can communicate more than before. But as artificial intelligence-based teachers do not have any kind of emotion, they cannot motivate and encourage the students. Similarly, students cannot share their happiness and sadness with an artificial intelligence-based teacher (Kaya et al.,2022). Moreover, an artificial intelligence-based teacher cannot provide the precise imagination and creativity that a human-based teacher may provide (Nalbant et al., 2021).

2.1.2.2 Non-Human Teacher

According to human characteristics, it is quite uncertain whether students will be able to trust and respect machine-based artificial intelligence in the same way that they trust

a human-based teacher. Similarly, an artificial intelligence-based teacher may not be a role model similar to a human teacher for the students to follow (Kaya et al.,2022).

2.1.2.3 Unemployment Issue

Artificial intelligence can undoubtedly provide a significant positive impact in education sector as it is capable of many things. As a result, it may replace humans in many sectors and thus will create unemployment situations (Nalbant et al., 2021).

2.1.2.4 High Cost

Complex machines like artificial intelligence can be costly. Similarly, its maintenance and repair costs might be expensive as well. So, it might be hard for a school system to carry out the expense (Nalbant et al., 2021).

2.1.2.5 Distribution Imbalance

To ensure overall impacts of artificial intelligence in education, it is necessary to keep significant and latest technologies inside an educational institution. These technologies often considered as expensive to buy, modify or update. As buying and maintaining artificial intelligence is costly, all educational institutions might be unable to keep all the supplies at once. Thus, it will create a distribution imbalance which will also create imbalance in overall learning process. Some institutions will have more advanced technology while others will get less developed or no technology at all (Nalbant et al., 2021). As a result, some students will gain significant knowledge with the aid of artificial intelligence and the others will miss the deep learning.

2.1.2.6 Negative Impact on Social Life and Health

A student is more benefited by achieving personalized, adaptive learning with artificial intelligence. With the use of virtual reality, the student is gaining more knowledge. But it is damaging his social life. As a student is getting help more in technology, he is not getting enough time with his classmates or teachers. Thus, they are becoming socially isolated which often cause depression (Nalbant et al., 2021).

Moreover, it can cause health problems as well. Being isolated can make a student depressed. It can also create some health problems like eye disorders, and waist, wrist, and neck pain while having more time with technology (Nalbant et al., 2021).

2.1.2.7 Systemic Problem

As artificial intelligence is becoming a trending topic in recent days, many new technologies are being created and tested. Many technologies have not been tested yet. Therefore, it is still uncertain whether it is going to make a positive impact or not. Moreover, it is using students' data to ensure a tailored education system. As a result, it will create a bias if data are fallen into the wrong hand (Kaya et al.,2022).

However, different authors have mentioned different models to achieve various impacts on this topic as Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Models & Impacts

MODELS	IMPACTS	REFERENCE
Language Model	Chatbot is created based on language model which enables personalized learning, automated grading & interactive learning	Sok and Heng, 2023; Baidoo-Anu et al., 2023
User Modelling	It helps to create student profiling. As a result, it provides a tailored education system for individual student	Huang et al., 2023
Student Model	It enables a personalized & adaptive learning	Nassoura, 2022; Chassignol et al., 2018; Ahmad et al., 2020; Guan et al., 2020; Southgate et al., 2019

Student Profile Modeling	It helps to generate student profiling & can predict students' future performance.	Missaoui and Maalel, 2021; Guan et al., 2020
Predictive Model	It is used to predict a student's performance and his possibility of dropout.	Salas-Pilco and Yang, 2022; Ahmad et al., 2020; Al Braiki et al., 2020; Guan et al., 2020; Remian, 2019; Chen et al., 2020
Personalized Education Model	It creates personalized learning for each individual student	Kaya & Bulut, 2022;
Generative Model	It enables personalized & adaptive tutoring. It also helps to automate grading and in providing feedback.	Baidoo-Anu et al., 2023
Bayesian Model	It detects student progress so that it can prevent a student from dropout and also provide personalized learning.	Dimitriadou et al., 2023
Instructional Model	It helps to enhance teaching experience	Ahmad et al., 2020; Asad et al., 2021
Personalized Training Model	It helps to generate personalized learning	Nalbant, 2021

Learner Model	It enables personalized & adaptive learning, prevents dropout intentions, and helps to continuous progress monitoring	Akinwalere & Ivanov, 2022; Guan et al., 2020; Chen et al.,2020
Evaluation Model	It helps to evaluate students' assessments	Krasheninnik et al., 2022
Open Learner Models (OLMs)	It is used to support personalized and adaptive learning & enhance intelligent tutoring system	Ahmad et al., 2020
AI Based Teaching Model	It helps to generate intelligent teaching robots	Kaya & Bulut, 2022
Assessment-Based Learning Environment (ABLE) model	It is used to support virtual reality for better learning outcomes	Nigar,N.,2022
Naïve Bayes Models	It helps for grading, evaluation & prevent dropout	Ahmad et al., 2020
Logistic Regression Model	It helps to predict future performance of students	Ahmad et al., 2020

Chapter 3 : METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Objective

The objective of this article is to examine the impact of artificial intelligence in education specially in academic sector. The article tends to give an overview in both positive and negative impacts of artificial intelligence in education sector with reviewing existing articles.

3.2 Search Strategy

To identify relevant papers on the impact of artificial intelligence in education, a comprehensive search was conducted on Google Scholar. Keywords like “artificial intelligence”, “AI”, “impact”, “education” etc. were used to select relevant articles. Articles from 2018 to 2023 were reviewed in order to get recent knowledge about the impact of artificial intelligence in education.

3.3 Selection Criteria

The papers which were addressing the impact of artificial intelligence in education was reviewed. Moreover, prioritizing papers which discussed specific artificial intelligence’s applications in education, such as personalized and adaptive learning, automated grading and feedback, or online learning.

Chapter 4 : RESULT & DISCUSSION

The current review article aims to analyze the impacts of artificial intelligence in the education sector based on past studies. The findings of several studies suggest that artificial intelligence can immensely keep impacting the education sector, especially in enhancing learning outcomes. For example, personalized and adaptive learning, which utilizes machine learning and data mining algorithms to collect and analyze student data related to attitude, behavior, and needs, has shown a significant improvement in students' overall performance (Hashim et al., 2022; Baidoo-Anu et al., 2023; Krstić et al., 2022). Therefore, artificial intelligence can offer a tailored education system for each and every student.

Furthermore, chatbots can be another alternative option for personalized and adaptive learning (Baidoo-Anu et al., 2023; Sok and Heng, 2023; Nalbant, 2021). Research has revealed that chatbots do not just offer personalized learning but also interactive learning and automated grading.

In addition, artificial intelligence assists to provide distance education, benefiting both teachers and students (Kaya & Bulut, 2022; Dimitriadou et al., 2023). Students can seek and gain knowledge globally at any place at any time, while teachers can share their expertise from anywhere as per students' demand.

Moreover, artificial intelligence can ensure an intelligent tutoring system and intelligent robots which can enhance a student's learning and address his weak point (Remian, 2019; Nassoura, 2022). Besides, a smart campus with smart content can be achieved with the aid of artificial intelligence (Southgate et al., 2019; Ahmad et al., 2022). Using advanced artificial intelligence technologies such as- virtual reality and chatbots can be defined as a smart campus. Virtual reality can be a tremendous solution when learning

becomes risky and costly (Dimitriadou et al., 2023; Guan et al., 2020; Mijwil et al., 2022). Similarly, gamification can be an example of smart content which can significantly improve students' learning outcomes (Penny, 2021).

In addition, artificial intelligence can serve as a valuable tool for evaluating students through exams (Krstić et al., 2022; Nalbant, 2021; Akinwalere & Ivanov, 2022). For instance, it can take answer scripts from students and then evaluates them in a standardized manner. Also, it can detect cheating and plagiarism also which can make a student's work authentic and valuable.

However, despite the positive impacts, there are also negative implications to consider. For example, in point of money, artificial intelligence technologies might not be suitable to use. Artificial intelligence technologies seem to be costly to buy, maintain, and repair. As an educational institution with a low budget, it is hard to maintain those artificial intelligence tools (Nalbant, 2021). The author also found that as financial arrangements differ from one institution to another, it is difficult to keep the same technologies among various institutions.

Moreover, it might replace teachers, leading to potential unemployment issues (Nalbant, 2021). Furthermore, the lack of emotional capabilities in artificial intelligence-based teachers raises questions about the student's trust respect, and willingness to share personal experiences with him (Kaya & Bulut, 2022; Nalbant, 2021).

On top of that, as artificial intelligence's implementation in education is still ongoing, its impact on education platforms remains uncertain (Kaya & Bulut, 2022). Lastly, ethical concerns may arise as the collected data can create chaos as the collected data may fall into the wrong hands (Nalbant, 2021).

Chapter 5 : LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Since the implementation of artificial intelligence in education is a recent topic these days, it has not yet been fully developed. As a result, it is difficult to confine all the impacts so far to one place. Therefore, many new impacts may be discussed in the future. Similarly, new technologies may be listed in the near future.

Chapter 6 : CONTRIBUTION

The present study attempts to address the impacts of artificial intelligence. First, the study extends the limited research on understanding the impacts of artificial intelligence in today's learning progress. Second, existing research work on artificial intelligence in education has primarily focused on the positive impact rather than exploring the positive and negative impacts simultaneously. This article reviews both the positive and negative impacts for getting a better understanding. Finally, this article has reviewed the latest relevant articles which will help getting a clear overview of the impact of artificial intelligence in education in recent years.

Chapter 7 : CONCLUSION

The present review article has reviewed the impacts of artificial intelligence in education research from 2018 to 2023 and then it describes the impacts based on the findings. Based on the findings, it is clearly proved that artificial intelligence has a tremendous impact in the education sector. These impacts can either be positive or negative. For instance, it can provide personalized learning, personalized feedback, distance education, and a smart campus. On the other hand, it may cause unemployment issues, financial issues, and ethical issues which can be referred to as negative impacts. Even though it has some negative impacts, artificial intelligence undoubtedly has some potential to enhance students learning to a new level. But the fact needs to remember that the development of this is still in its early stages. As a result, more research may be needed to understand its complete impact on students' learning.

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